

1 **Original Research Paper**

2 **Title: Potentials of using milk performance data and FAMACHA score as indicators for**
3 **Targeted Selective Treatment in Lacaune dairy sheep in Switzerland**

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22 **Abstract**

23 Targeted Selective Treatment (TST) is one approach to slow down the development of
24 anthelmintic resistance. Its success is closely linked to the correct identification of animals in
25 need of treatment. In dairy goats it has been proposed to use milk yield as TST indicator and to
26 focus treatments on high yielding dairy goats. In dairy sheep the relation between milk
27 performance and infection with gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN) is not well known. The aim of
28 this study was to investigate the relation between milk yield and GIN infection in dairy sheep and

29 based on this, to evaluate milk performance data as a potential TST indicator. Overall 1159
30 Lacaune ewes of 15 dairy sheep farms in Switzerland were included in the study. The ewes were
31 phenotyped once between August and December 2019, when they were at least 70 days in milk
32 (DIM). Individual faecal samples were taken from every ewe to determine the nematode egg
33 excretion per gram faeces (EPG). Further collected parameters were test day milk yield and test
34 day milk protein content, which were closely time-related to faecal analyses, lactation number,
35 DIM and the proportion of *Haemonchus contortus* on farm level. For ewes sampled ≥ 200 DIM,
36 data of 200-day milk yield and 200-day milk protein content was also obtained. In addition, the
37 clinical parameters FAMACHA score and packed cell volume (PCV) were measured. Faecal egg
38 count reduction tests (FECRT) were conducted on 4 and 3 farms to test the efficacy of moxidectin
39 and levamisole, respectively. Linear mixed models were used to analyse the effects of the
40 collected parameters on EPG. EPG increased significantly with increasing test day milk yields
41 ($P < 0.01$), indicating high yielding ewes to be less resistant to GIN infections than low yielding
42 ewes. The effect was most pronounced in the earlier lactation stage but remained within a
43 moderate range. FECRT showed effective treatments of moxidectin and levamisole on all except
44 one farm, where resistance against moxidectin occurred. Overall, our results indicated the
45 potential of using milk yield as TST indicator in dairy sheep. As dairy sheep farmers usually avoid
46 anthelmintic treatment during lactation, TST of high yielding ewes in the dry period based on
47 milk yield data of rather early lactation might be suggested. On farms with predominantly
48 *H. contortus* the combination with FAMACHA might improve the correct identification of highly
49 infected ewes, as FAMACHA was correlated with EPG ($r = 0.37$, $P < 0.001$).

50

51 Keywords

52 Gastrointestinal nematodes; dairy sheep; milk yield; targeted selective treatment; organic
53 farming; anthelmintic resistance

54 **1 Introduction**

55 In sheep farming, gastrointestinal nematode (GIN) infections are among the most important
56 diseases, causing high economic losses due to reduced performance and animal health
57 problems (Morgan et al., 2013). As a result of improper use and high treatment frequencies, the
58 worldwide increase of resistance to anthelmintics has become a central challenge in sheep
59 farming. Since the 1970s, numerous studies of anthelmintic resistance (AR) in GIN have been
60 published worldwide (Kaplan, 2004). Increasingly, multiple-drug resistant GIN are also occurring
61 in Europe (Scheuerle et al., 2009; Voigt et al., 2012; Traversa and Von Samson-
62 Himmelstjerna, 2016). This highlights the urgent need to develop sustainable strategies for
63 parasite control in small ruminants. In dairy systems, the pressure to act is increased by the
64 limitation to few anthelmintic drugs, which are allowed to use during lactation, if milk is intended
65 for human consumption.

66

67 The impact of parasitism on productivity in dairy sheep has been explored in previous studies and
68 there seems to be a general agreement that GIN infections reduce milk production in dairy
69 ewes. A meta-analysis quantified the mean loss in milk yield to 22 % in infected compared to
70 uninfected dairy sheep (Mavrot et al., 2015). Effective anthelmintic treatment of infected dairy
71 ewes appears to lead to longer milking periods (Suarez et al., 2009), improved lactation
72 persistence (Fthenakis et al., 2005) and lower somatic cell counts (Arsenopoulos et al., 2019),
73 whereas effects of GIN infections on milk components are not consistent across studies. While
74 Sechi et al. (2010) did not find effects of GIN infection on milk components, Cruz-Rojo et al.
75 (2012) reported lower total milk protein contents.

76

77 Usually, dairy sheep farmers try to keep anthelmintic treatments of ewes during lactation to a
78 minimum, as the subsequent withholding periods for milk will have negative impacts on their
79 returns. This particularly affects organic farming, where legally required milk withdrawal times
80 usually double after anthelmintic treatment (Bio Suisse, 2020). As a result, there is a risk that
81 dairy sheep farmers tend to systematically treat all ewes in the dry period in order to avoid milk

82 losses and animal welfare problems during lactation. This conflicts with refugia-based methods,
83 which are considered essential to slow down the development of AR. The phenomenon of refugia
84 is based on leaving a part of the parasite population unexposed to anthelmintic treatment in order
85 to maintain genotypes of parasites still susceptible to the anthelmintic drug (Van Wyk, 2001).
86 Whole herd anthelmintic treatments during the dry period, especially during winter, may kill all
87 susceptible GIN. Thus, after lambing and at the beginning of the grazing period, only eggs of
88 resistant GIN would be excreted on the relatively clean pastures in spring, which might select
89 strongly for AR. However, the described pattern may differ between farms, as lambing periods
90 can vary depending on farm management and dairy sheep breeds. Targeted selective treatment
91 (TST) implements the refugia based approach as TST is aiming to treat only animals in need of
92 treatment and/or animals which are responsible for most of pasture contamination, while aiming
93 to sustain animal productivity (Kenyon et al., 2009). Usually, only few individuals within a flock
94 are responsible for most of the egg excretion on pasture (Srèter et al., 1994). The success of TST
95 is therefore closely linked to identifying these animals within a flock based on corresponding
96 parameters. In order to integrate TST into field conditions, especially on large farms, it is
97 necessary to keep the costs and effort required to collect these parameters to a minimum
98 (Besier, 2008).

99

100 Monthly milk recordings provide dairy farmers with easily accessible data for each individual
101 animal. In contrast to other used TST indicators, such as eggs per gram of faeces (EPG) (Cringoli
102 et al., 2009; Gallidis et al., 2009), anthelmintic treatment based on milk performance data would
103 therefore involve only minimum additional effort or costs for data collection and analysis.
104 However, this is only applicable to farms, which are already included in official milk recording
105 schemes.

106 In dairy goats, milk yield and lactation number has been reported to be possible indicators for
107 TST. In the studies of Hoste and Chartier (1993) and Hoste et al. (1999, as cited in Hoste et
108 al., 2002) goats with high milk yield and first lactating goats caused the highest egg excretions in
109 a herd. TST of these animal groups allowed an efficient control of GIN infections while

110 maintaining animal productivity (Hoste et al., 2002). In dairy sheep, there are still very few
111 studies on this topic and the relation between milk performance and EPG is not well known.
112 Previous studies using milk yield as TST indicator in dairy sheep did not investigate the
113 correlation between EPG and milk yield, but they relied on the assumption of the same relation
114 between milk performance and EPG in sheep as in goats (Cringoli et al., 2009; Gallidis et al.,
115 2009). However, Hoste et al. (2006) could not find a significant difference in egg excretion
116 between high and low yielding dairy ewes. Regarding the lactation number a significant effect on
117 egg excretion was found, as first lactating dairy ewes had higher EPG than dairy ewes with higher
118 lactation numbers.

119

120 The FAMACHA score has been proposed to be a reliable indicator to identify sheep, which are
121 in need of treatment due to infections with *H. contortus* (Bath and Van Wyk, 2001). This has been
122 shown in several studies, where significant correlations between FAMACHA and packed cell
123 volume (PCV) have been found (Kaplan et al., 2004; Papadopoulos et al., 2013; Chylinski et al.,
124 2015). As TST indicator, the FAMACHA score should also be able to reflect *H. contortus*-related
125 EPG, but findings are not consistent across studies. Kaplan et al. (2004), Burke et al. (2007) and
126 Notter et al. (2017) found significant correlations between FAMACHA and EPG ranging from
127 0.21 to 0.44, whereas in other studies no relation was identified (Chilinsky et al., 2015; Moors
128 and Gaulty, 2009). All of these studies investigated mixed GIN infections, except for Chylinski et
129 al. (2015), where ewes were artificially infected with *H. contortus*. As most studies have been
130 performed in non-dairy sheep, results of using the FAMACHA score in dairy sheep breeds is
131 limited.

132

133 The aim of this study was therefore (i) to investigate the general relation between milk
134 performance and GIN infections in a Swiss Lacaune dairy sheep subpopulation and based on this,
135 to evaluate milk performance data as a potential TST indicator for dairy sheep farms.
136 Furthermore, (ii) the application of the FAMACHA score in Lacaune dairy ewes as additional

137 TST indicator was to be tested and (iii) faecal egg count reduction tests (FECRT) should provide
138 insight into the current situation of anthelmintic resistance in Swiss dairy sheep farms.

139 2 Materials and methods

140 All animal-related procedures were following the Swiss animal welfare act, the animal welfare
141 ordinance as well as the animal experimentation ordinance. The responsible authority (Cantonal
142 Veterinary Office, Aargau, Switzerland; permission No. 75730) has given its approval to the
143 present study.

144

145 2.1 Study design and animals

146 Overall data of 1159 lactating Lacaune dairy sheep were used in the study. The data were
147 collected from August to December 2019 on 15 commercial dairy sheep farms in Switzerland.
148 Selection criteria for dairy sheep farms included: (i) a herd size of at least 30 animals, (ii) breeding
149 pure-bred Lacaune dairy sheep (female sheep of at least 87.5 % Lacaune blood), (iii) all ewes
150 have access to pasture during the vegetation period, (iv) availability of milk performance data and
151 (v) no anthelmintic treatment was given during the current lactation period. Of the included dairy
152 sheep farms 14 were managed according to the organic farming standards in Switzerland (Bio
153 Suisse, 2020).

154 All farms were visited once for data collection, where all ewes were sampled which were at least
155 70 days in milk (DIM). Only one farm was visited twice to increase the number of ewes meeting
156 the requirement of ≥ 70 DIM. To achieve a high degree of temporal agreement between all
157 parameters, there were no more than 3 days between official milk recordings and farm
158 visits, except for one farm, where the difference between milk recording and farm visit was 10
159 days.

160

161 2.2 Faecal egg counts, larval culture and identification

162 Faecal samples were taken directly from the rectum of each animal. The samples used for EPG
163 determination were transported in cool boxes and stored at approximately 5°C for 1 to maximal
164 4 days in the laboratory until further examination. EPG were determined by using a McMaster
165 egg-counting technique: 4 g of homogenised faeces were mixed with approximately 10 ml
166 of flotation suspension (saturated salt solution; density 1.2 g/cm³). The mixture was sieved in a

167 measuring cylinder and the flotation suspension was added up to a total volume of 60 ml. The
168 suspension was mixed and immediately filled into two counting fields of a McMaster counting
169 chamber. After 10 minutes the chambers were examined at 100x magnification with one counted
170 egg representing 50 EPG.

171 On each farm, 2-5 pooled samples of at least 10 % randomly selected ewes were taken to conduct
172 larval culture. For small herds faecal samples were taken from at least 10 animals. The faecal
173 samples used for larval cultures were transported and stored at room temperature. The cultures
174 were incubated at 25°C and 80 % humidity for 10 – 14 days. One-hundred 3rd stage larvae from
175 every pooled sample were then differentiated under the microscope in *H. contortus* and other GIN
176 of the order Strongylida according to keys provided by Deplazes et al. (2013). The mean value of
177 the proportion of *H. contortus* was calculated from the pooled samples for each farm.

178

179 *2.3 Performance data*

180 Performance data of all ewes were provided by the Swiss Dairy Sheep Farming Cooperative. For
181 each animal the results of test day milk yield (kg), test day milk protein (%), lactation number and
182 the date of lambing of the current lactation were obtained. DIM was calculated for each animal as
183 the difference between lambing date and date of the farm visit. For ewes sampled at ≥ 200 DIM,
184 data of the 200-day milk yield (kg) and the mean 200-day milk protein content (%) were also
185 obtained.

186

187 *2.4 Faecal egg count reduction test (FECRT)*

188 FECRTs were performed to test the efficacy of moxidectin (Cydectin[®] 0.1 %, oral suspension)
189 and levamisole (Endex[®] 8.75 %, oral suspension) on 4 and 3 of the monitored farms, respectively.
190 For every FECRT a group of 10-15 sheep was selected at the end of lactation with $EPG \geq 300$ as
191 recommended by Cabaret and Berrag (2004), based on the last EPG results obtained. Where this
192 was not feasible, animals with lower EPG were also included. Only on one farm the
193 ewelambs were sampled for FECRT. The ewelambs grazed on the same pastures as the lactating
194 ewes throughout the year. The anthelmintic products were dosed according to the manufacturer's

195 instructions. Faecal samples were collected before drenching and 10-14 days post-
196 treatment. EPG were determined using the same method as described above, but the minimum
197 detection level was set to 16.7 EPG.

198

199 *2.5 PCV and FAMACHA score*

200 Blood samples were taken from jugular vein puncture in 2 ml EDTA vacutainer tubes for
201 subsequent PCV determination and were kept at 5°C until one hour before the examination to
202 bring the samples to room temperature. PCV was determined within 24 hours using the
203 microhematocrit method. Therefore, blood samples were filled into microhematocrit tubes and
204 centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 5 min (Heraus, Pico 17 Centrifuge). The FAMACHA score was
205 used to classify the ocular mucosa colour of each animal into one of the five categories (1-5) as
206 described by Van Wyk and Bath (2002).

207

208 *2.6 Statistical analyses*

209 All statistical analyses were performed in R 3.6.1 (R Core Team, 2019). Two linear mixed effect
210 models were calculated to assess the impact of the collected parameters on EPG, using
211 the lmer function from the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015). In Model 1 (M1) test day milk
212 yield, test day milk protein, lactation number, DIM, the proportion of *H. contortus* and an
213 interaction between test day milk yield and DIM were included as fixed effects. The farm was
214 considered as a random effect to correct for any dependencies between ewes within the same
215 farm. In Model 2 (M2) the fixed effects were the 200-day milk yield, 200-day milk protein
216 content, DIM, lactation number and the proportion of *H. contortus*, whereas the farm was
217 considered again as random effect. For M2 the dataset was reduced to only these animals, which
218 were sampled at ≥ 200 DIM. Residuals of both models were graphically evaluated to ensure the
219 model assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity. For both models EPG was transformed to
220 meet the assumption of normality of residuals by using the transformation $\log(\text{EPG} +$
221 40). Spearman correlation coefficients were calculated to estimate the correlations between EPG

222 and test day milk yield and of the FAMACHA score with PCV and EPG. FECRTs and
223 corresponding 95 % credible intervals (CI) were determined using the function fecr_stan from
224 the R-package eggCounts 2.3 (Wang et al., 2018). For calculations, a paired design model with
225 individual efficacy was used. As recommended by Wang et al. (2018) the 2.5 % and 97.5 %
226 percentiles as the 95 % CI and the median as the summary statistics were used. Observations with
227 zero EPG pre-treatment were excluded prior to the analysis.

228 3 Results

229 3.1 Descriptive statistics and data handling

230 Overall data of 1159 lactating ewes were collected in the present study. The number of sampled
231 ewes per farm varied between 17 and 199 animals with a mean of 77 animals per farm. On one
232 farm ≤ 30 ewes were sampled, as only 17 ewes met the requirement of ≥ 70 DIM at the time of
233 data collection. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of all variables collected in the study. It
234 was not possible to obtain a complete data set with all parameters from all ewes, because of
235 insufficient faecal material or incomplete milk performance records. That was the case for 33 and
236 47 ewes, respectively. In addition, there were 25 observations with missing test day milk protein,
237 due to insufficient milk quantities at milk recordings, which were handled as missing values. One
238 outlier for EPG was removed, because of very high EPG and < 2 g of faeces. Therefore, M1 and
239 M2 were calculated based on sample sizes with $n_1 = 1053$ and $n_2 = 505$.

240

241 3.2 Linear mixed models

242 M1 revealed a relation between the test day milk yield and logEPG ($P < 0.01$), showing increasing
243 logEPG with increasing milk yields. Further, there was an interaction between test day milk yield
244 and DIM ($P < 0.05$), which is presented in Figure 1 for 70 and 200 DIM. The relation between
245 test day milk yield and logEPG was most pronounced at the earliest time of lactation covered in
246 our study (70 DIM) and decreased towards the end of lactation. All other fixed effects were not
247 statistically significant, but the lactation number and the proportion of *H. contortus* showed values
248 tending towards significance ($P = 0.07$ and $P = 0.06$, respectively). Figure 2 shows the relation
249 between the proportion of *H. contortus* and logEPG. Equation 1 was developed to predict back
250 transformed EPG from all included fixed effects in M1:

251

$$252 \text{ EPG} = \exp(4,242 + 0,4845x_1 + (-0,001695)x_2 + 0,03342x_3 + 0,08284x_4 + 0,01628x_5 \\ 253 \quad + (-0,002114)x_1x_2) - 40$$

254

255 where x_1 = test day milk yield (kg), x_2 =DIM, x_3 = lactation number, x_4 = test day milk protein
256 (%), x_5 = percentage of *H. contortus*.

(1)

257

258 Exemplary calculations using Equation 1 for ewes with high (3 kg) and low milk yields (1 kg) at
259 70 DIM, while keeping all other predictors adjusted to their mean, resulted in about 310 EPG
260 higher egg excretions in the high yielding ewes. Towards the end of lactation (200 DIM) the same
261 calculations resulted in a difference of 26 EPG, with higher EPG in high yielding ewes. The
262 correlation coefficient between EPG and test day milk yield was in a moderate range ($r = 0.31$, P
263 > 0.001).

264

265 In M2 the lactation number was the only fixed effect that showed a relation with logEPG ($P <$
266 0.05), indicating increasing EPG with higher lactation numbers (Figure 3). However, the relation
267 between EPG and lactation numbers ≥ 8 was difficult to estimate due to the low number of ewes
268 with high lactation numbers. Neither the 200-day milk yield nor the 200-day milk protein content
269 had an effect on logEPG ($P = 0.89$ and $P = 0.91$, respectively).

270

271 *3.3 Larval culture and identification*

272 The proportion of *H. contortus* varied on the farms between 4.3 and 97.3 %, with a mean of
273 43.3 %. Figure 4 reports the prevalence of *H. contortus* and other GIN of the order Strongylida
274 for each farm.

275

276 *3.4 PCV and FAMACHA score*

277 The FAMACHA score was correlated with PCV ($r = -0.32$; $P < 0.001$) and EPG ($r = 0.15$; $P <$
278 0.001). Including only farms in the analysis, where *H. contortus* was the predominant parasite (\geq
279 50 %), the correlation coefficients increased to $r = -0.48$ ($P < 0.001$) and $r = 0.37$ ($P < 0.001$) for
280 PCV and EPG (Fig. 5), respectively.

281

282 *3.5 FECRTs*

283 The results of the FECRTs are presented in Table 2. On Farm 2 only 6 and 9 sheep with
284 moxidectin and levamisole treatment, respectively, were included in FECRTs, due to zero counts
285 pre-treatment. According to the World Association for the Advancement of Veterinary
286 Parasitology guidelines (WAAVP) (Coles et al., 1992; Levecke et al., 2018) the results of the
287 FECRTs indicated the occurrence of AR against moxidectin on one farm (farm 5), as the mean
288 reduction percentage was $\leq 95\%$ and the lower CI $\leq 90\%$. AR against levamisole was suspected
289 on two farms (farm 1 and 5), based on the classification criteria of either the mean reduction
290 percentage or the lower CI is $\leq 95\%$ and $\leq 90\%$, respectively.

291 **4 Discussion**

292 TST is one approach to reduce the selection pressure for AR. It relies on the correct identification
293 of animals that are in need of treatment due to GIN infections (Kenyon et al., 2009). The aim of
294 this study was therefore to investigate the general relation between milk performance and GIN
295 infection and to evaluate the potential of milk performance data as an indicator for TST in Swiss
296 Lacaune dairy sheep. Overall, this study showed that higher test day milk yields were associated
297 with higher EPG. This relation was most pronounced during the earliest stage of lactation covered
298 in this study.

299

300 In the present study the ewes were sampled when they were at least 70 DIM. This cut-off date
301 was chosen because this study was performed within a project that was designed to investigate
302 the possibility of breeding for improved resistance to GIN infections in sheep. In this context it
303 was necessary to have a phenotype with data of at least two milk recordings available for each
304 ewe at the time of faecal analysis. In Lacaune dairy sheep the lactation peak occurs
305 between the 27th and 48th day postpartum depending on the lactation number. Until the 90th day,
306 50 % of the total milk yield is usually produced (Elvira et al., 2013). Thus, in this study we
307 covered only the two last thirds of the lactation period where milk yield is already decreasing.

308

309 It has been postulated that immune functions compete for scarce nutrients with other body
310 functions during high nutritional demand periods, e.g. late pregnancy and lactation, whereas the
311 reproductive functions are prioritised over immune functions (Coop and Kyriazakis, 1999).
312 Consequently, during the time of highest nutrient requirements for milk production, the
313 penalisation of immune functions would be expected to be most pronounced. This is supported
314 by findings of Notter et al. (2017), where ewes with two or more lambs were less resistant to GIN
315 infections than single-rearing ewes from lambing to 60 days postpartum. With decreasing milk
316 yields towards the end of the lactation period, it can be assumed that the competition for scarce
317 nutrients between milk production and immune functions is no longer present. This
318 would account for the observed decreasing relation between test day milk yield and EPG towards

319 the end of lactation in M1. Our exemplary calculations for 200 DIM have shown a small
320 difference of 26 EPG between high (3 kg) and low (1 kg) yielding ewes. At 70 DIM the difference
321 was more apparent (310 EPG) but remained within a moderate range. This seems to be in
322 accordance with Houdjik et al. (2003), suggesting that there is no total absence of immune
323 functions against GIN in sheep, even in times of scarce nutrients.

324 The effect of test day milk yield on EPG observed in our study is in contrast to findings of Hoste
325 et al. (2006), who didn't observe a relation between the milk production level and EPG in dairy
326 sheep. The differing results might be due to the low mean infection level (< 200 EPG) in the study
327 of Hoste et al. (2006). Our analyses were based on a large sample size, which allowed to detect
328 even small effect sizes, but only a single measurement of EPG was determined per animal
329 between 70 and 385 DIM. We are aware that repeated measurements of EPG within the same
330 ewes would have allowed an improved estimation of the susceptibility to GIN infections of the
331 ewes. However, we assume that a single EPG determination may be sufficient to classify an ewe
332 being rather resistant or susceptible to GIN infections. This is supported by the study of Notter et
333 al. (2017), who found correlations between EPG determined at different times of lactation within
334 the same ewes, although this study covered only the time of the periparturient period until the 60th
335 day postpartum.

336

337 Cringoli et al. (2009) and Gallidis et al. (2009) have already used milk yield data as TST indicator
338 in dairy sheep but did not investigate the general relation between milk yield and EPG. Cringoli
339 et al. (2009) treated all ewes with milk yields above the flock mean, based on the assumption, that
340 high yielding ewes are more susceptible to GIN infections than low yielding ewes. However, no
341 conclusions of the effect of TST on milk performance and the parasitological status of the ewes
342 could be drawn from this study. Gallidis et al. (2009) did not evaluate the impact of TST on milk
343 performance, but in regard to the parasitological status, a comparable control of GIN infection of
344 a systematically treated group and treatment of high yielding ewes only (> 2 litres), has been
345 observed. The positive relation between test day milk yield and EPG observed in our study
346 supports the approach to focus anthelmintic treatment on high yielding ewes. However, the

347 potential of milk yield data to estimate the GIN infection level was indicated to be dependent on
348 the lactation stage of the ewes. Milk yield records from late lactation stage did not seem to be
349 suitable to identify ewes in need of treatment due to the weak relation with EPG in this stage of
350 lactation. This suggests the limitation of milk yield data as TST indicator to early and mid-
351 lactation.

352

353 The effect of milk protein content on EPG was evaluated, because of the demand of the immune
354 system for metabolisable protein and its sensitivity to protein scarcity (Houdijk, 2012). In our
355 analyses no effect of milk protein content was found in either model. This is supported by results
356 of Sechi et al. (2010) who did not find differences in milk protein contents between different
357 infection levels in ewes. In contrast, findings of Cruz-Rojo et al. (2012) suggested a lower milk
358 protein content in dairy ewes due to parasitic infection. Based on our results and due to the
359 conflicting findings of other studies, we suggest that milk protein content is not suitable as an
360 indicator for TST in dairy sheep.

361

362 Both our models indicated a positive relation between lactation number and EPG, as with
363 increasing lactation numbers also EPG increased. The absolute differences of EPG between
364 different lactation numbers varied in a low range, as calculations with Equation 1 predict an
365 increase of approximately 7 EPG per lactation number. These results do not support findings of
366 previous studies, which indicated primiparous ewes to be less resistant to GIN infections
367 compared to multiparous ewes (Hoste et al., 2006; Sechi et al., 2010). Hoste et al. (2006)
368 suggested to focus anthelmintic treatment on first lactating ewes and hypothesised, that the low
369 immune response of primiparous ewes might be due to the lack of or the little previous exposure
370 to GIN. Most farms in our study were managed according to the organic farming standards in
371 Switzerland (Bio Suisse, 2020), where access to pasture is mandatory. Therefore, primiparous
372 ewes might have already been sufficiently exposed to GIN as lambs and were able to develop a
373 good immune defence to GIN infections before the first lactation. Our results do not suggest the
374 lactation number being a suitable indicator for ewes in need of treatment. Instead, it may be

375 considered to combine daily milk yield data of rather early stages of lactation with other already
376 evaluated TST indicators. The FAMACHA score might improve the precision of identifying ewes
377 with high GIN infection levels, as FAMACHA showed a moderate correlation with EPG in our
378 study ($r = 0.37$). However, this applies only to farms, where *H. contortus* is the predominant GIN,
379 as the correlation between FAMACHA and EPG was low ($r = 0.15$) when farms with $< 50\%$ *H.*
380 *contortus* were included in the analysis. Burke et al. (2007) and Notter et al. (2017) have reported
381 similar results, indicating the FAMACHA score to be a valuable tool to support TST decisions if
382 *H. contortus* is present in relevant proportions. The combination with the body condition score
383 (BCS) might be a further possibility, as BCS has been suggested to be a suitable TST indicator in
384 sheep and does not require high effort for its implementation (Cornelius et al., 2014; Calvete et
385 al., 2020). Calvete et al. (2020) proposed to treat all ewes with $BCS \leq 3$ in the period prior to
386 mating and lambing, which resulted in improved productivity of ewes and lambs.

387

388 The timing of anthelmintic treatment in dairy farms is of particular concern, as the required
389 withholding periods of anthelmintic drugs for milk must be taken into account. Most farmers
390 participating in this study did not treat any ewes during lactation, with few exceptions for
391 individual animals when clinical signs appeared (e.g. bottle jaw). If farmers used anthelmintic
392 drugs, they usually treated all ewes in the dry period prior to lambing to avoid salvage treatments
393 during subsequent lactation. Performance data, which is closely time related to the dry period of
394 the ewes is the 200-day milk yield, since the average lactation length in Lacaune dairy sheep is
395 around 224 days (Elvira et al., 2013). In M2 we tested therefore the potential of the 200-day milk
396 yield as TST indicator in dairy sheep for anthelmintic treatments in the dry period. However, the
397 200-day milk performance does not seem to be suitable to identify animals in need of treatment
398 at the end of lactation.

399

400 In Switzerland, *H. contortus* appears to have a high prevalence (Rinaldi et al., 2015), which is in
401 accordance with our results. The proportion of *H. contortus* was included in the models to account
402 for its high fecundity compared to other trichostrongylids (Cabaret et al., 1998; Saccareau et al.,

403 2017). As expected, with an increasing proportion of *H. contortus* an increase of EPG was
404 observed.

405 For *H. contortus* the phenomenon of arrested development in the host to survive winter periods
406 in temperate climates is well known (Waller et al., 2004; Langrova et al., 2008), as well as the
407 high susceptibility of its free-living larvae to unfavourable climate conditions (O'Connor et al.,
408 2006). The resumption of development of the inhibited larvae is closely linked to the
409 periparturient phase in ewes, leading to high nematode egg excretion around lambing, which can
410 be a major source of pasture contamination with infective larvae in spring (Procter and Gibbs,
411 1968). It has been shown that anthelmintic treatment of ewes prior to lambing is able to suppress
412 the periparturient relaxation in immunity (PPRI) in ewes (Procter and Gibbs, 1968).
413 Consequently, it should reduce pasture contamination and subsequent reinfection. Notter et al.
414 (2017) observed a repetitive pattern of the extent of the PPRI in ewes, indicating that the PPRI is
415 approximately the same every year within the same ewe. With this knowledge, we assume that it
416 should be possible to drench ewes during the dry period according to the test day milk yields of
417 their previous early to mid-lactation. As those ewes should also show a distinct PPRI after
418 lambing, this procedure may help to reduce pasture contamination, thus may also reduce the
419 infection pressure for untreated animals and lowering the risk of salvage treatments during that
420 grazing period.

421

422 However, further studies would be necessary to explore these relations and the effects of TST
423 (based on milk yield data) in the dry period on the next lactation period in terms of the
424 parasitological status and milk performance of ewes. Moreover, further research is also needed to
425 investigate, if the association between milk yield data and EPG might be improved by using milk
426 yield data of < 70 DIM.

427

428 To ensure the efficacy of TST, it is essential to use effective anthelmintics for treatment. Recent
429 information of AR in dairy sheep farms in Switzerland is very limited. The results of the present
430 study showed that the occurrence of AR is also present on Swiss dairy sheep farms. This situation

431 has become especially visible on farm 5, where according to the WAAVP guidelines (Coles et
432 al., 1992) the efficacy of moxidectin was reduced and AR against levamisole was suspected. The
433 result of the occurrence of AR against moxidectin on farm 5 must be regarded carefully due to
434 the low pre-treatment EPG of 115.3 and the wide range of the 95 % CI (82.0 – 97.5). Low pre-
435 treatment EPG can underestimate the efficacy of anthelmintics in FECRTs (Levecke et al., 2012).
436 Furthermore, the results of a McMaster analysis are susceptible to high variability. Yet the
437 variation in results can be reduced, but not eliminated, by using more sensitive methods (Togerson
438 et al., 2012). In the present study, in order to take this variability into account, the minimum
439 detection limit of the McMaster method was lowered to 16.7 EPG. AR against moxidectin was
440 also found in Germany (Scheuerle et al., 2009) and in the Netherlands (Ploeger and Everts, 2018),
441 whereas a review summarising the current situation of AR in sheep in Europe has indicated that
442 moxidectin is still one of the most effective anthelmintics and the efficacy of levamisole is clearly
443 reduced (Traversa and Samson-Himmelstjerna, 2016). The overall results of all FECRTs in this
444 study might indicate that the problem of AR is not as prevalent in dairy sheep farms in Switzerland
445 yet. All tested farms had groups of ewes lambing at different times in the year, resulting in
446 alternating dry periods. Consequently, not all ewes were treated at the same time during the
447 previous years and thus, refugia for susceptible parasites in the untreated groups of ewes were
448 maintained, which might have slowed down the development of resistance.

449 It has also to be considered that all farms included in FECRTs were managed according to the
450 organic farming standards in Switzerland. Following the principles of organic farming, most
451 farmers were aiming to limit the use of anthelmintic drugs. In addition, farmers avoided whole
452 herd treatments during lactation, due to doubled withholding periods for milk after drenching,
453 causing milk losses for 10 and 14 days for moxidectin and levamisole, respectively.
454 Consequently, the results of FECRTs in non-organic dairy sheep farms in Switzerland might have
455 been different.

456 **5 Conclusion**

457 Dairy sheep farmers usually avoid anthelmintic treatment during lactation due to the withholding
458 periods for milk and tend to treat all ewes during the dry period. The targeted treatment prior to
459 lambing of only ewes in need for treatment could be an approach to slow down the development
460 of anthelmintic resistance and reduce pasture contamination in spring and subsequent reinfection.
461 Our results showed a positive relation between daily milk yield and EPG in Swiss Lacaune dairy
462 sheep, indicating high yielding ewes to be less resistant to GIN infections than low yielding ewes.
463 The effect was most pronounced in the earlier stage of lactation, suggesting the potential of using
464 milk yield data of earlier lactation as indicator for TST in the subsequent dry period. In farms
465 with predominantly *H. contortus*, treatment decisions could be supported by the application of
466 the FAMACHA score.

467

468

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663

664

665 **Table 1.**

666 Descriptive statistics of phenotypes collected on the 15 dairy sheep farms (n = 1053, except for
667 200-day milk yield and 200-day milk protein content, where n = 505).

668

variable	mean	standard deviation	min	max
EPG	876.1	2359.6	0	24100
test day milk yield (kg)	1.3	0.7	0.2	4.3
test day milk protein (%)	6.3	0.9	3.6	9.9
DIM	195	71	70	385
lactation number	3.1	2.0	1	11
200-day milk yield (kg)	465.1	111.2	167.0	894.0
200-day milk protein content (%)	5.2	0.4	4.1	6.6

669

670 **Table 2.**

671 Mean faecal egg count reduction test percentages (FECRT %) and 95 % credible intervals (CI) of
672 moxidectin and levamisole tested on 4 dairy sheep farms in Switzerland.

673

Farm	n	AM	mean pre-t EPG (min, max)	mean post-t EPG (min, max)	FECR %	low CI	high CI
1	13	mox	1206.4 (233.3 – 2966.7)	34.6 (0 – 200.0)	97.4	95.1	98.7
2	6	mox	361.1 (33.3 – 1000.0)	0	99.5	95.6	100
5	12	mox	115.3 (33.3 – 400.0)	9.7 (0 – 66.7)	92.5	82.0	97.5
13	16	mox	1055.0 (100.0 – 1667.0)	0	99.9	99.7	100
1	11	lev	1016.7 (50.0 – 2650.0)	25.8 (0 – 50.0)	95.7	88.1	98.2
2	9	lev	272.2 (16.7 – 1133.2)	0	99.6	96.2	100
5	11	lev	292.4 (16.7 – 933.3)	9.1 (0 – 33.3)	95.9	88.1	98.8

AM = anthelmintic, mox = moxidectin, lev = levamisole, pre-t = pre-treatment, post-t = post-treatment.

674

675 **Figure Captions**

676

677 **Fig. 1.** Scatterplot of test day milk yields (kg) versus log(EPG + 40) for all animals included in
678 the calculations of M1 (n = 1053). Regression lines with confidence intervals predicted from M1
679 for 70 and 200 DIM.

680

681 **Fig. 2.** Scatterplot of the proportion of *H. contortus* versus log(EPG+40) for all animals included
682 in the calculations of M1 (n = 1053). Regression line with confidence intervals predicted from
683 M1.

684

685 **Fig. 3.** Scatterplot of lactation number versus log(EPG + 40) for all animals sampled ≥ 200 DIM
 686 (n = 505). Regression line and confidence interval predicted from M2.

687

688 **Fig. 4.** Percentage of 3rd stage larvae of *H. contortus* and other gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN)
 689 of the order Strongylida found in coprocultures of the 15 dairy sheep farms.

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694 **Fig. 5.** Scatterplot of the FAMACHA score versus EPG of all animals on farms with
695 predominantly *H. contortus* ($\geq 50\%$) (n= 410). A random jitter was added to the data points to
696 visualise their density.

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